

METHODS OF ADVERTISING'S PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT ON THE PERSON

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Abstract. In each country, advertising is aimed at the audience of this country, it is intended for the population of a particular country. The only thing is that the products and services consumed in different countries coincide, but at the same time advertising has its own characteristics and affects the carriers of a particular language culture. In this article, we have described the psychology of advertising and the effectiveness of its impact.

Keywords: advertising, personality, psyche, consumer, buyer, observation.

Аннотация. В каждой стране реклама ориентирована на аудиторию этой страны, она предназначена для населения конкретной страны. Дело в том, что товары и услуги, потребляемые в разных странах, совпадают, но при этом реклама имеет свои особенности и воздействует на носителей той или иной языковой культуры. В данной статье мы описали психологию рекламы и эффективность её воздействия.

Ключевые слова: реклама, личность, психика, потребитель, покупатель, наблюдение.

Introduction. The effectiveness of the psychological impact of advertising media is characterized by the number of consumers, the brightness and depth of the impression left in the human memory by these media, the degree of attention. The effectiveness of the psychological impact of advertising on the consumer can be determined by conducting observations, experiments, surveys.

The observation method is used to study the impact of individual advertising media on consumers. This method is passive, since the observer leads the buyer. The observation method allows you to assess the psychological impact of advertising in natural conditions, when the consumer directly interacts with a particular advertising medium. Along with the observation method, the experimental method is also widely used. This method is an active method. Here, the study of the psychological impact of advertising is carried out in conditions artificially created by the experimenter.

The experimenter can create various combinations of buyers in order to select the most successful one. The survey method also refers to active methods for determining the psychological impact of advertising. This method is laborious, but more reliable than others, since it allows you to directly determine the attitude of the buyer himself not only to the advertising medium as a whole, but also to individual structural elements of this medium.

Using the survey method, you can evaluate the impact of an advertising medium on buyers and determine which elements of its design attract the most attention and are better remembered.

Discussion. Data on the effectiveness of the psychological impact of advertising make it possible to estimate its effectiveness. Above, we have considered some aspects of the general

theoretical foundations of the organization of advertising. However, since the topic of our work is focused on the advertising of complex technical goods, we will try to analyze what special requirements are imposed on it, what are its specific features, how an advertising company is built in this area. So, each trade network has its own characteristics, and accordingly, the advertising activities of each trading enterprise should take into account the characteristics of the goods it specializes in selling.

Here it is necessary to remember two aspects of advertising: when advertising one of the product groups, you must simultaneously adhere to all the general rules and regulations of advertising and take into account the specific features of a particular product group.[1]

Conclusion and analysis. A clear and precise idea of the specific product itself is required. Therefore, we will give a brief description of the complex technical product group. This group includes, first of all, household electrical appliances and household electronic equipment. It is worth noting that the life cycle of goods belonging to this group is currently at the stage of maturity in our country. This means that these products have already firmly established themselves in the domestic market and the volume of sales in this area is quite stable, although its growth is not as high as in the previous stage, but at this stage the competition is very strong and the assortment of products in this group is constantly expanding and updating.

The latter feature is one of the most important in relation to the group of complex technical goods. Here the connection between trade and scientific and technological progress is clearly manifested: currently, manufacturing companies, on the one hand, are constantly producing more and more improved models of already existing technologies and equipment; on the other hand, they strive to create fundamentally new goods, which in fact often leads to the combination of the properties of one or more complex technical goods in one new product. Here it is necessary to recall once again the life cycle of the product: it is natural that completely new products begin their "life" on the market from the stage of formation, but in the field of complex technical goods, things are not so simple.[2]

As we have already said, over the past decade, there have been almost no completely new products that are completely unknown to the consumer, which are a combination of various new modifications and features. Therefore, we still refer complex technical goods to the third stage of the life cycle. Another feature of this group of products is that each model has its own, extensive and, as a rule, complex technical characteristics.

The advertiser's task in this regard is to correctly determine which of them can be positively distinguished in the advertising message. Here you need to feel the permissible limit: presenting the technical advantages of the product in too much detail can be incomprehensible or simply boring for some groups of potential consumers. At the same time, it is necessary to emphasize that these advantages are sufficient to convince the audience of the advantages of choosing this product. A skillfully balanced description of the complex technical product being advertised makes the advertising message more effective.[3]

Specific requirements for the arrangement and design of shop windows in stores are also associated with the technical characteristics of this group of goods. Complex technical goods should be displayed so that the consumer can see all the advantages of the design and get the most complete idea of the technical capabilities of the product. Many complex technical goods are tested directly in the sales and exhibition hall, so the room should be equipped with all the

necessary devices for connecting electrical outlets to the power source of the machine or equipment.[4]

The presence of trained, qualified sales consultants on the trading floor who are able to provide clear and understandable information about the functioning and structure of the goods, the differences between one model and another, etc. is mandatory. Unlike a relatively short advertising message (we have discussed the requirements above), the verbal description of the sales assistant should be more detailed. However, here too, it is necessary to avoid situations where the potential buyer is bombarded with technical details. Much depends on the seller's tact, his ability to act in communication situations. It is not for nothing that in the previous paragraphs of our work we paid great attention to the specifics of advertising practice in our country and various advertising tools.

When working in the field of trade in complex technical goods, it is necessary to take into account the general level of economic development, socio-political factors, taking into account the national and regional characteristics of the market in different regions of the country. This requires a high level of awareness of the current state of affairs in a particular region of the company's activity, as well as the average income of the population, the nature of demand and beyond. All this allows you to competently form the assortment and conduct advertising activities in accordance with the real situation in the local market.

Conclusion. Speaking about the effectiveness of advertising complex technical goods, we consider it appropriate to note that another important factor, in addition to those mentioned above, also affects the growth of turnover in this area. It is established that the actual service life of the equipment corresponds to that indicated in the warranty for the product. It should be remembered that the warranty period must fully correspond to the technical capabilities of the goods.

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